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Modeling DCA Strategies for Supporting Multimedia Services with QoS over Cellular Communication Systems

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Abstract – The increasing demand for advanced services in cellular networks such as data and video raises the problem of efficient bandwidth management in terms of channel availability. Many algorithms for supporting advanced services have been presented in the literature based mainly on bandwidth reservation and capacity management. In this paper, novel dynamic channel assignment strategies for supporting data (e.g. file transfer) and video (video viewing, video conference) with Quality of Service (QoS), and their evaluation through a prototype advanced statistical simulation environment for cellular communications are presented. Moreover, we analyze the dynamic and distributed channel allocation of data and video channels based on signal purity measures. Finally, the performance of the proposed algorithms evaluated through a prototype simulation environment is discussed.

Key-words: - cellular network, multimedia services, simulation environment, channel assignment

1 Introduction

1.1 cellular networks and channel assignment

In cellular networks, the whole coverage area is divided in hexagonal smaller areas called cells. Base Stations (BSs) are distributed among the network cells. Thus, the connected users are served within the local cell or neighbor cells. The network BSs are connected together with Base Station Controllers (BSCs). BSs and BSCs, supports also the user movement from one cell to another. The channel assignment to mobile users (MU) is made due to new call arrival or reallocation (handoff). The management of available channels within each cell is prescribed by channel assignment strategies.

The cellular network capacity (how many users can be served at the same time) is strongly connected with channel availability. The available bandwidth (interpreted as the number of available channels) is restricted but the number of mobile users is increasing day by day[1].

The channel assignment to cells or mobile users is one of the fundamental resource management issues in a mobile communication system[2].

The main goals of a channel assignment strategy are:

- Minimize the probability of blocking new calls (no available channel for a new user)
- Minimize the probability of dropping ongoing calls (due to unsuccessful handoff)
- Minimize the interference between co-channel users

Three are the most known channel assignment categories according to literature:

- FCA - Fixed Channel Assignment
- DCA - Dynamic Channel Assignment
- HCA - Hybrid Channel Assignment

Based on a pre-estimated traffic, a set of channels are permanently allocated to each cell intensity with regard to FCA [3,4,5,6,7]. In DCA [3,8,9,10,11], the available channels are assigned to new and existing users in a dynamically manner. Thus, DCA strategy is more flexible compared to dynamically change of traffic conditions. Finally, HCA [3,12] combines the features of FCA and DCA.

1.2 Advanced services and QoS

In recent years, the user demand for advanced mobile services such as data transfer, video, etc, bring out much more the problem of the available bandwidth. The algorithm design for efficient

bandwidth management is a critical issue for multimedia cellular network design.

Quality of service (QoS) can be studied from many different points of view. In cellular communications the bandwidth management is a key concept for achieving the desired QoS. Many bandwidth management strategies have been proposed such as bandwidth reservation, reducing handoff dropping probability [13,14,15], etc. In these studies, the handoff dropping probability in combination with the new call admission are the most critical factors that affect the QoS assurance for advanced cellular services [13,14,15]. In general, QoS prescribes the required capacity (bits per second) that has to be above a specified threshold until the service normal termination. The QoS constraints are based on the type of each new call service. The dynamically changing network traffic conditions make difficult the optimal performance of bandwidth management algorithms. In our approach, the proposed algorithms ensure the required capacity until the normal service termination. Most of the studies found in [16] do not take in consideration the signal measures for supporting QoS as our study does.

2 Prototype Simulation Environment

2.1 Introduction

In our model, the cellular network consists of N cell with a BS in each cell center. Connected users may exist in various positions within a cell according to a pre-defined mesh of spots. The network modeling is focused to network procedures that support the main user activities.

2.2 Basic network procedures

The simulation model supports four major network procedures which are :

- New call arrival
- Call Termination
- Call Reallocation
- User Movement

New call arrival is based on Poisson distribution (eq. 1) with regard to a daily traffic model.

$$P(x) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \cdot \lambda^x}{x!} \quad (1)$$

where λ , represents the new call arrival rate. After a new call arrival, the selected channel assignment scheme is activated. Based on the selected scheme,

the algorithm searches for an available channel, calculates CNR between MU and BS, and finally calculates the interference between current MU and other co-channel users. If the signal purity conditions (Carrier to Noise plus Interference Ratio Threshold - CNIR Threshold) are fulfilled, the channel is finally assigned to that MU. Multiple channels are assigned in case of video services. An unsuccessful channel assignment procedure causes a new blocked call.

The call termination procedure, examines the call holding time for each service (except data service) and disconnects the current MU if this time is expired.

In every simulation step, the signal purity for each connected user is examined. As in new call arrival, CNR and CNIR for one or more channels (for the same MU) are calculated. If the final CNIR for current MU is below the pre-defined threshold, the call reallocation procedure tries to find another accepted channel. When this attempt is not successful, the call is dropped.

Finally, a user movement is generated according to Gaussian distribution (eq. 2).

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-x^2/2} \quad (2)$$

2.3 User mobility model

As mentioned before, the λ parameter represents the new call arrival rate. This rate is analogous to the time of the day. A fixed set of simulation time steps represents a whole day according to representation of a defined real time slice with a single simulation step. Each zone represents a specific percentage period of the day. The parameter λ , changes with regard to each active zone in simulation time.

2.4 Implementation architecture

2.4.1 Agent-Based Systems

An Agent can be described as a computational system that interacts autonomously with its environment and operates for the goal for which it has been designed [17]. It perceives the environment conditions, acts according to that conditions, interprets perceptions and solves problems [18]. Agents are entities that are smaller than a typical application [19]. Additional information about the most known characteristics of agents such as adaptability, autonomy, interactivity, etc, can be found in [20,21,22,23,24]. In modern problems, a number of agents are needed for modeling all the system aspects and so the multi-agent systems

emerged. Multi-agent systems (MAS), can be faced as a loosely coupled network of problem-solver entities [25] that collaborate together with the common goal to solve the whole problem. According to literature, agent technology has been used for distributed resource management in telecommunication systems [26,27,28].

2.4.2 Agent-based model for cellular network

A key point for the simulation system development is the adaptation to real network behavior. In a real network, when a user tries for a call, at the same time another service for another user is terminated and so on. Due to that fact the above mentioned network procedures must be implemented in a concurrent manner.

Every network procedure, is independent from each other, acts autonomously, interacts with environment (cellular network), has its own goals and thus can be implemented as agent.

2.4.3 Multi-Agent layered Architecture

The architecture of the prototype simulation system is based on the multi-agent concept, adapted to real cellular network behavior.

According to this architecture, the whole system is divided to three layers (fig. 1):

- Layer 1 (core layer) which represents the cellular network environment and where the basic events take place
- Layer 2 consists of four agents that implement the concurrent events and describe the network behavior
- Layer 3 which contains the scheduler (Control Agent)

The scheduler (control agent) controls and synchronizes the Agent activities. Contains a clock for agent activation in layer-2 and assures the correct execution order of any supplementary function.

2.4.4 The scheduler

Each agent is implemented as thread within the Java Virtual Machine (JVM) environment. Thus, the scheduler synchronizes the thread operation and activation. Our environment constitutes a discrete event simulator.

The scheduler (control agent) synchronizes three actions (fig. 2) which are:

- Initial procedures (supplementary procedures for each new simulation step)
- Event Agents (New call arrival, Call reallocation, User movement and Call termination)
- Final procedures (after completion of each simulation step)

Fig. 1 - Multi-Agent Layered Architecture

Fig. 2 - Scheduler (Control Agent)

3 Proposed DCA algorithms for supporting advanced services with QoS

3.1 Supported novel DCA schemes

Our simulation system supports four basic and two hybrid DCA schemes which are:

Basic DCA schemes

- Unbalanced (UDCA)
- Balanced (BDCA)
- Best CNR (CDCA)
- Round Blocking (RDCA)

Hybrid DCA schemes

- CNR and Balanced hybrid (CBDCA)
- Hybrid DCA (HDCA)

In Unbalanced version[29], the network makes one try for user connection within the initiated cell (where the new call occurred).

Round blocking scheme is an extension of unbalanced variation which searches also for an accepted channel in the neighbor cells. The algorithm stops when a successful channel assignment is made.

To maintain balanced network conditions, the Balanced variation[30] is developed. According to this algorithm, the final attempt for a MU connection is made within the cell (initiated or neighbor) with the minimum congestion.

In Best CNR variation[30], the system calculates the CNR between MU and BS of initiated or neighbor cell. The final attempt for connection is made within the cell with maximum CNR between BS and MU. Thus, we achieve better shield of MU from interference.

The goal of CNR and Balanced hybrid variation[30] (fig. 3) is to shield more the channel from interference and at the same time to maintain balanced traffic conditions in the network.

Try to find the best three least congested cells within the neighbor cells

if not possible,
apply Best CNR for all cells,
end of algorithm

Else
Apply Best CNR in the best three least congested cells

fig. 3 - CNR and Balanced hybrid variation

The hybrid DCA algorithm[30] (fig. 4), exhausts all the possibilities for a successful channel assignment in the neighbor and maintains balanced traffic conditions in the network.

Try to find the three best least congested cells within the neighbor cells

If not possible,
apply Best CNR for all cells,
end of algorithm

Else
Try to establish call in each least congested cell (in a round blocking manner)

fig. 4 - Hybrid DCA

3.2 Proposed DCA variations for supporting Multimedia services

3.2.1 Service Generation

The Poisson distribution determines the potential users to be connected. Based on three different Gaussian distributions the system generates the type of service (voice, data, video) and the requested capacity (video) or size (data). Initially, the type of service is generated (table 1).

X	Service Type
[0.5,0.5]	Voice
[-0.8,-0.5]U(0.5,0.8]	Data
[-1.0,-0.8]U(0.8,1.0]	Video

Table 1. Service type generation

If the service is voice, a typical channel is given to that user. In case of Data service the required file size for transfer is generated (table 2).

X	File size
[-0.5,0.5]	100Kbytes
[-0.7,-0.5]U(0.5,0.7]	500Kbytes
[-0.9,-0.7]U(0.7,0.9]	1Mbyte
[-1.0,-0.9]U(0.9,1.0]	5Mbyte

Table 2. File size generation

For video service, the corresponding required capacity (table 3) is generated.

X	Capacity
[-0.5,0.5]	384000bps
[-0.7,-0.5]U(0.5,0.7]	768000bps
[-0.85,-0.7]U(0.7,0.85]	1536000bps
[-1.0,-0.85]U(0.85,1.0]	3072000bps

Table 3. Capacity generation

3.2.2 Multimedia Unbalanced DCA (MUDCA)

A voice service requires only a single channel. The call holding time (CHT) is resulted from exponential distribution with selected mean value. The CHT is combined with current simulation time, where each simulation step corresponds with a constant real time slice. The call termination agent, checks in every simulation step the call progress of each connected user in terms of simulation time. When this time is expired, the call is terminated.

For each new data service, a single channel is assigned. This is because the service is not real time. In each simulation step, the capacity of the assigned channel is calculated. According to this capacity, an amount of data is subtracted (fig. 5) from the previous requested (previous simulation step). When the initially requested data are transferred, the service is terminated. In this case, the CHT is replaced with active channel capacity in combination with the transferred data.

When a video service is initiated, the requested capacity is covered using multiple channels according to the selected DCA scheme. This is a real

time service, requires QoS and so the initially requested capacity must be warranted until the call termination. The algorithm for channel assignment calculates the total capacity among various channels and stops the assignment when the requested capacity is covered or the six neighbor cells have been checked. Figure 6, shows the algorithm for channel allocation that used for new video call arrival or video call reallocation.

```
//Data call progress and termination
//a specific real time slice is assigned to a single sim step
//SD=Simulation step duration (sec)
Get remaining data (RD) to be transferred (user registry)
Get current channel capacity (CCAP)//connected ch.
New_RD=RD-(CCAP*SD)
If (RD<=0)
    Terminate Data Call
Else
    Do nothing
```

Fig. 5. Data call progress and Termination

The reallocation agent, checks one by one each connected channel for that service and tries to reallocate only specific channels that not fulfill the CNIR threshold. After the partial reallocation the new total capacity (remaining and new channels) is re-calculated. If the new capacity is not accepted, the reallocation agent continuous to search for appropriate channels.

```
//new channel assignment for video call
Rcap=requested capacity by video call (QoS service)
Attempt=0
Capserved=0 //total served capacity
While ((Capserved<Rcap) && (attempt<=6*Chnum))
    Find an available channel
    Newserved=0
    If available channel is found
        Calculate CNR between BS and MU
        Calculate interference from other co-channels
        Calculate final CNIR
        If (CNIR>=CNIR threshold)
            Calculate current channel capacity
            Newserved=current channel capacity
            Store channel attributes in User registry
        End if
    End if
    Attempt++
    If (Newserved>0) Capserved+=Newserved
End while
If (Capserved>=Rcap) succeed=1
Else succeed=0
```

Fig. 6. channel assignment algorithm for video call

3.2.3 Multiple Cell-Multiple channel Multimedia Unbalanced DCA (MCCMUDCA)

In MCCMUDCA variation, the MUDCA is used among different cells in the neighbor. Thus, multiple

channels can be assigned from different cells for supporting a video call. In figure 7, a video call is in progress in cell-1. The required capacity for that call is served via 1a,1b,1c and 1d channels that belong to cell-1 and cell-2. With this technique, low dropping and blocking probability can be achieved due to multiple channel availability among different neighbor cells.

Fig. 7. - Multiple channel assignment (MCCMUDCA)

4 Statistical metrics

4.1 Basic metrics

Blocking probability constitutes a measure for GoS[31] (Grade of Service) level or Quality of Service[32]. When a new call arrival occurs and the network can not allocate a channel then we say that this call is blocked. The blocking probability is calculated from the ratio

$$P_{blocking} = \frac{\text{number of blocked calls}}{\text{number of calls}} \quad (3)$$

The *dropping probability* is also an additional and very important characteristic of the cellular network. When a call is in progress and the required quality conditions are not met then this call is obligatory driven to termination. The dropping probability is calculated from the ratio

$$P_{fc} = \frac{\text{number of forced calls}}{\text{number of calls} - \text{number of blocked calls}} \quad (4)$$

Additional statistical metrics found in literature [30] can be used to measure the results accuracy using outliers[33] and simulation model behavior such as periodicity and standard deviation progress[30]. In this paper we present some preliminary results and so only the basic metrics have been used.

5 Simulation results

5.1 Sample executions

We have simulated a cellular network with 19 cells, 50 potential users in each cell and 32 channels per cell. For advanced services such as Data and video we have used the MUDCA variation. For voice services, we have simulated all the proposed DCA variations.

A new video service has initiated in cell 13 (fig. 9a, 9b). The reallocation agent checks each video channel individually and reports that no reallocation is needed. After the reallocation check, the user is moved to cell 1 (reconnection from cell 13 to 1), user position 3.

```
>>>NEW VIDEO[13][35]=384000, H/T=65.43178,
Cur.Sim.Time:0, f.hold:65.43178
Checking . . .
*** [13][35], BASIC channel (10.0), cap=191674.52
<<ACCEPTED>>
*** [13][35], X-Cell:13, X-Channel:11.0,
cap=184368.0 <<ACCEPTED>>
*** [13][35], X-Cell:13, X-Channel:12.0,
cap=186047.28 <<ACCEPTED>>
Reporting... for [13][35], Req.CAP=384000.0,
Lost.CAP=0.0, New.Served=384000.0,
Good.cap=562089.75 %GOOD, No Reallocation Needed
---> Disconnect VIDEO [13][35] for MOVE
@@ NEW VIDEO MOVEMENT successful, giving [1][3],
OLD H/T:65.43178
. . . . .
```

Fig. 9a. Video service initiation

After a new reallocation check (fig. 10b), two video channels are not accepted (rejected) and so reallocation must be made only for these channels. The algorithm finds two alternative channels, computes the corresponding capacity and finally decides for another reallocation trial or not. When the CHT is expired, the service is terminated.

```
Checking . . .
*** [1][3], BASIC channel (3.0), cap=173036.02
<<ACCEPTED>>
*** [1][3], X-Cell:1, X-Channel:1.0,
cap=165086.77 <<REJECTED>>
*** [1][3], X-Cell:1, X-Channel:4.0,
cap=176465.86 <<REJECTED>>
Reporting... for [1][3], Req.CAP=384000.0,
Lost.CAP=341552.62, New.Served=42447.375,
Good.cap=173036.02 %BAD!, Reallocation is needed
. . .
REALLOCATING [1][3] . . .
{0} - ### SUGGESTED Basic, [1][3],CH:16,
Req.Cap:210963, Cap:168810.73
{ C A P } - Total Capacity (SUGGESTED
Channels):168810.73
{1} - ### SUGGESTED Extra, [1][3],X.Cell:1,
X.Ch:17, Cap:173610.4
{ C A P } - Total Capacity (SUGGESTED
Channels):342421.12
Final record to [cell][user]=[1][3]
. . .
Checking . . .
*** [1][3], BASIC channel (16.0), cap=168810.73
<<ACCEPTED>>
```

```
*** [1][3], X-Cell:1, X-Channel:17.0,
cap=173610.4 <<ACCEPTED>>
*** [1][3], X-Cell:1, X-Channel:3.0,
cap=173036.02 <<ACCEPTED>>
Reporting... for [1][3], Req.CAP=384000.0,
Lost.CAP=0.0, New.Served=384000.0,
Good.cap=515457.12 %GOOD, No Reallocation Needed
---> VIDEO DISCONNECT Due to END OF TIME, [1][3]
```

Fig. 9b. Video reallocation

5.2 Performance results

Fig. 10. Blocking probability for VOICE services

Fig. 11. - Dropping probability for VOICE services

Fig. 12. Blocking probability for VOICE services (2 traffic days - MUDCA)

Fig. 13. Blocking probability for DATA services (2 traffic days - MUDCA)

Fig. 14. Blocking probability for VIDEO services (2 traffic days - MUDCA)

Fig. 15. Dropping probability for VIDEO services (2 traffic days - MUDCA)

6 Conclusions & Future work

Novel algorithms for supporting multimedia services such as Data and Video over cellular networks have been presented in this paper. Contrary to the most recent studies for supporting multimedia services with QoS, our proposed algorithms are based also on

signal measures such as CNR and CNIR for giving the requested capacity for a selected service.

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